

PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM CHARACTERISTICS OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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Annotation: *In this article, in the interpretation of lectures, which are one of the main forms of educational processes in secondary schools today, as a complex, multi-level process, the following series of features can be considered as their characteristics. information is provided.*

Keywords: *dialectic, periodicity, degree of validity, diversity, significance, risk, ability to describe educational methods, relevance to situations, ownership of a structural structure (structurality), manageability, social purpose, ability to differentiate, integrative.*

Today, there are a lot of opinions against the organization of lectures for school students, and the reasons are clearly and adequately justified by the authors. However, the main reason why we study the features of lecture classes is the organization of lectures in schools in the classroom and extracurricular processes, at various events organized for teachers and students, conferences and pedagogical studies. taken into account.

When interpreting lectures, which are one of the main forms of educational processes, as a complex, multi-level process, the following characteristics can be considered as their characteristics: dialectic, periodicity, degree of validity, conflict, significance, risk. , the ability to describe educational methods, relevance to situations, ownership of a structural structure (structurality), manageability, social purpose, ability to differentiate, integrativeness.[1]

Dialecticism is a process of improvement and development of lecture training, as a result of which its normative foundations are gradually updated, subject-subject (teacher-student) relations are formed. characterized by the arrival The resolution of subject-subject relations determines the development indicator of the lecture process.

Periodicity is expressed in the gradual transition from subject-object relations to subject-subject (teacher-pupils) relations.

The level of validity is expressed by the novelty, reliability and validity of the information, as well as compliance with the requirements of state educational standards.[2]

Discrimination is the possibility of weakening the desire and interest in students to think freely and independently, to listen and analyze the opinions of others, and to receive independent education and self-discipline. Most of the students do not have time to learn the information given by the speaker, and a high level of pedagogical competence is required from the speaker.

Importance - in addition to explaining the essence of the studied topic, it is possible to provide information about the topics studied in the course of practical training and independent education, as well as concepts that are important in the process of educational relations. Creation of grounds for active participation of students in the process of practical training.

Risk is related to probability properties. Due to the limited possibilities of determining the basic concepts of all students and objective assessment, the speaker feels a sense of risk and anxiety, which in turn affects the effectiveness of the pedagogical process.[3]

The ability to describe educational methods is the fact that a certain educational method cannot be used in arbitrary situations, that is, it cannot claim universality. It is necessary to pay attention to the importance of studying subjects in a mutually dependent manner, their consistency, and the possibility of studying subjects in parallel. It envisages the creation of subject-subject (teacher-student) relations on the basis of ensuring the activity of students.

Relevance to the situation. The effectiveness of the lecture training largely depends on the interest of the participants of this process, the level of initial understanding and the tendency of the educational environment to accept news and the situations that arise. The importance of the situational approach in the formation of a comfortable educational environment.

Structurality is the fact that the lecture session has a clear structural structure, that is, it consists of an introduction, a presentation of the content of the lecture, and final parts. In order to form the interest of the students and to coordinate their activities, to introduce the purpose and plan of the lecture and the recommended literature, to determine and objectively

evaluate the initial concepts of the students, to understand the concepts that are intended to be studied. substantiation of the need for mastery, presentation of the content of the lecture, conclusion and conclusion are expressed as the main stages of the lecture training.

Controllability - the availability of opportunities to design, model, and coordinate the activities of participants according to the circumstances of improvement and development processes.[4]

Social purpose. Coordination of interests based on state, society and personal needs. Based on the coordination of individual goals and tasks with the goals and tasks of the pedagogical system, it determines the prospects of self-development and personal development of the subjects of the pedagogical process.

Sorting ability. Availability of different approaches to ensure the activity of individual and groups. Excessive attention paid to a particular student or group of students affects the interest and activity of another student or group of students. Availability of opportunities for group formation and implementation of differentiated approaches.

Integrativeness is the mutual unity of internal and external factors that serve movement and development.

In the organization of integrative lectures, the educational process is imagined in the form of a whole dynamic system, and in the design of the educational content, through the integration of topics on the basis of consistency, that is, each topic is based on the essence of the topic that precedes it. it is necessary to take into account that it is studied in relation to each other [5].

Seminar classes, which are considered one of the main forms of the pedagogical process organized in schools, are organized based on concepts independently learned by students, as well as information given during lectures. Training is important in creating the necessary conditions and opportunities for students to actively participate in the course of the seminar, to find a positive solution to the assigned tasks, and to successfully communicate with the participants and partners.

The characteristics of the seminar-training sessions include the wide range of possibilities for creating the process of interaction between students in this process, students using different communication styles depending on the situations that arise in the process of interaction. learning, mastering communicative skills and competences, the most important thing is to bring students the formation of skills such as communicating with people with different individual psychological

characteristics, that is, developing their own communication styles and realizing their individuality possible.[6]

According to researchers, training is one of the most important methods for ensuring the effectiveness of the educational process. Communication skills are formed in students in the educational process based on this method. As a result of the students' interaction during the training process, they develop the skills of using different communication methods.

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